

Regenerative Endodontics – Case Report and Review of Literature of Biologically Based Treatment of Immature Permanent Tooth

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ABSTRACT

Background: The treatment of immature, necrotic teeth has undergone a significant change, with biologically based concepts and regenerative endodontic protocols replacing old 'apexification' methods. Initial investigations indicate that stem and progenitor cells derived from the pulp and/or periodontium play a role in ongoing root formation when regeneration techniques are employed.

Methodology: A mandibular premolar tooth with a long lasting infection at the tip of the root was cleaned using sodium hypochlorite and minimal tools. It was then treated with a paste containing three antibiotics: ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and amoxicillin. During a follow-up appointment, a blood clot was induced in the canal by irritating the periapical tissues. The canal was then sealed using mineral trioxide aggregate, glass ionomer cement, and composite resin.

Results: The apical periodontitis and the draining sinus were resolved, while the root maturation and apical closure persisted over a span of 18 months. The tooth exhibited a heightened sensitivity to pulp sensibility testing.

Conclusion: Dentists must acknowledge the significant potential of regenerative endodontics in treating necrotic, immature teeth. The initial approach should consist of irrigating with sodium hypochlorite only. Calcium hydroxide and other intra-canal medicaments should not be used since they hinder the formation of roots. This research utilizes a modified version of the tri-antibiotic paste, which is generally suggested for regenerative operations. The modification aims to prevent the discoloration of the crown that is typically associated with existing protocols. Regenerative endodontics, coupled with ongoing root growth, can potentially decrease the likelihood of fracture and premature tooth loss commonly associated with conventional 'apexification' techniques, which result in a thin and weak root structure.

Keywords: Teeth; Antibiotics: Ciprofloxacin, Metronidazole

INTRODUCTION

The restoration of blood supply to a necrotic pulp after a traumatic event, such as the complete removal of a tooth with an immature root, is a widely accepted and desirable outcome. This process promotes the continued growth of the tooth's root^[1]. In this clinical setting, the pulp is nonviable but not contaminated, and it can serve as a framework to facilitate the regrowth of blood vessels in the tooth. Utilizing the most effective methods for replantation, promptly performing the procedure to limit the likelihood of infection, and having an open apex larger than 1.1mm all enhance the probability of successful revascularization^[2]. Several recent studies have documented the ongoing growth of roots and the restoration of pulp sensitivity in treated necrotic immature teeth with infected root canals, even in cases with draining sinus tracts^[3]. The regenerative endodontic operations and revascularization of the root canal in teeth with diseased root canal systems have been referred to as a significant change in the treatment protocol for endodontic care^[4,5].

The conventional approach for treating immature teeth with infected root canal systems was referred to as 'apexification'. This comprised using calcium hydroxide as a medication within the root canal to eradicate the infection within the tooth's roots and gradually stimulate the formation of a barrier at the tip of the root (6). A root filling could only be finished after numerous visits and a lengthy time period, often lasting 12 months on average, was met. A more modern approach, known as the 'apexification' technique, utilizes the application of mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) to create an artificial barrier that promotes the formation of a hard tissue barrier. One benefit of this procedure is that it is typically accomplished within one or two consultations. Nevertheless, the utilization of 'apexification' methods including the application of either calcium hydroxide or MTA has often failed to facilitate ongoing root maturation. Therefore, the presence of thin dentinal walls and early tooth loss significantly increases the likelihood of experiencing a fracture.

Regenerative methods typically involve the application of a tri antibiotic paste to eradicate the infection within the root canal, which is considered essential for achieving success^[7]. The tri-antibiotic paste utilized in these studies comprises a blend of ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and minocycline. This combination has demonstrated consistent efficacy in eradicating bacteria present in infected root dentin, whereas the individual drugs used in isolation only resulted in significant reduction but not complete elimination of the bacteria. Additionally, research has demonstrated that this medicine combination effectively eradicates germs in the innermost layers of root canal dentin^[8,9,10,11]. Nevertheless, a drawback of this method is the occurrence of tooth discoloration, perhaps caused by the minocycline. Ledermix, a medication manufactured by Lederle Pharmaceutical in Wolfratshausen, Germany, contains tetracycline and has been found to produce more discoloration in teeth that are not fully developed compared to teeth that have fully matured. Lin et al. conducted a study on the antibacterial effectiveness of different combinations of antibiotics. They discovered that when amoxicillin was used as the third antibiotic together with ciprofloxacin and metronidazole, it was equally effective as minocycline in eradicating bacteria^[12]. Nevertheless, there is currently no documented evidence of regenerative procedures employing a tri-antibiotic paste that incorporates amoxicillin in its composition, nor is it known whether this particular combination leads to discoloration of the tooth's crown^[13]. Sensitivity and allergy to penicillin are a potential risk, which may make it unsuitable for certain people^[14]. This case report presents a method of endodontic regeneration involving the use of ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and amoxicillin

for the treatment of a mandibular left second premolar. The tooth in question was identified with pulpal necrosis, an infected root canal system, and a persistent periapical abscess.

CASE REPORT

A 13-year-old female patient visited our center's outpatient department to have her mandibular left second premolar examined. The medical history provided no relevant information. The patient did not have any pain or discomfort with the tooth. Her only issue was occasional poor breath, but her mother noticed some swelling of the gum next to the lower left second premolar. A thorough inspection inside the oral cavity showed that the tooth is undamaged and there are no indications of tooth decay, and there is no record of any previous injury. (Figure 1) shows the presence of a substantial draining sinus in the buccal gingiva. The mandibular left second premolar exhibited no response to both cold and electric pulp sensibility testing, but the other teeth in the lower left arch shown responsiveness. Periodontal probing revealed normal attachment levels with no probing depths above 3 mm. The tooth exhibited normal physiological mobility. There were no observed changes in the color of the crown (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Photograph depicting the teeth located in the back part of the left lower jaw. There is noticeable inflammation and a localized collection of pus next to the lower second premolar.

Radiographically, the mandibular left second premolar had an increase in the periodontal ligament space, incomplete root formation and a diffuse periapical radiolucency 5mm x 3 mm in size (Figure 2). No carious lesion was evident. A gutta-percha point was placed in the sinus tract and illustrated the relationship between the lesion and the periapical radiolucency (Figure 3).

Figure 2: This periapical radiograph shows a radiolucency around the lower left mandibular second premolar. An observation is made of a narrow dentinal wall near the tip of the root, which has a broad opening. No cavities are detected.

Figure 3: Radiograph showing a gutta-percha point inserted into the sinus tract that leads to the radiolucent area at the apex of the tooth..

The clinical and radiological examination confirmed a diagnosis of pulpal necrosis, an infected root canal system, and persistent periapical abscess. The illness was believed to have originated from a cracked occlusal tubercle, which allowed germs to contaminate the pulp. Given the root development stage, the maturity of the thin dentinal wall, and the wide open apex, pulpal regeneration was considered the most favorable treatment option. An extensive examination of the potential hazards, complexities, and alternate methods of therapy was conducted, and approval from the parents was acquired.

Local anesthesia was applied and rubber dam used to isolate the mandibular left second premolar. The access preparation involved the use of an operating microscope to visualize a single, broad canal. Drainage of haemorrhagic, purulent exudate was successfully achieved. The working length was determined using an apex locator and confirmed with a periapical radiograph acquired with a size 15 K-file. The file was positioned meticulously to minimize any potential harm to the canal walls. Prior to drying the canal using paper points, the canal was irrigated with 30 mL of 1% sodium hypochlorite, 2 mm from the working length. The tri-antibiotic paste comprised a 20mg powder of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and amoxicillin, combined with 1 ml of sterile water. The paste was meticulously inserted into the canal using a lentulo spiral root canal filler, with the aim of minimizing its placement in the upper part of the tooth. It was filled up to just below the cemento-enamel junction. The access chamber was sealed using a 4mm layer of Cavit (ESPE, Seefeld, Germany) and a 2mm layer of Fuji IX (GC, IL, USA).

The tooth underwent evaluation three weeks subsequent to its initial examination. The patient experienced pain three days after the surgery, for which they took oral analgesics (Ibuprofen). However, they have been symptom-free since then. Orally, the sinus that was draining has been resolved. However, as a result of the painful experience, it was determined that the tooth needed to be treated again. During rubber dam isolation, the canal was flushed with 20 ml of sodium hypochlorite, which was subjected to ultrasonic agitation using a size 10 K-file for one minute after each 5 ml was supplied. The canal was subsequently dehydrated and treated again with the previously indicated tri-antibiotic paste mixture, using the same method of application.

The patient was summoned again after an additional three weeks, stating that the tooth had remained without symptoms during that entire period. A periapical radiograph was obtained and showed that some Cavit material had been displaced towards the apex of the root canal. During rubber dam isolation, the canal was flushed with 10ml of sodium hypochlorite while using ultrasonic agitation for one minute after every 5ml of solution. Once the infection and foreign material were brought under control, the regenerative process was initiated. Following the removal of moisture from the canal using paper points, a D11T NiTi hand spreader (manufactured by Dentsply Tulsa Dental, TN, USA) was employed to stimulate the apical tissue until bleeding occurred in the root canal area. This was done to establish a biological scaffold that would facilitate the regenerative process (Figure 4). During a 15-minute interval, the blood was let to coagulate until it reached a point 3 mm below the cemento-enamel junction. Next, a 3mm layer of ProRoot white MTA was carefully inserted using a Lee block and Buchanan Pluggers. The access cavity was sealed using a 3mm layer of Fuji IX and a 2mm layer of acid etched composite resin Figure 5.

Figure 4: Clinical picture of the tooth where bleeding has been evoked by irritating the periapical tissues with a D11T instrument.

Figure 5: Radiographic image following placement of MTA to a level 3 mm below the cemento-enamel junction. The access cavity is filled with glass ionomer cement and composite resin. The radio-opaque material at the apical border is Cavif.

The tooth remained asymptomatic over an 18-month follow-up period. Clinically, the tooth was responsive to electric pulp sensibility testing while earlier testing throughout the follow-up period had been inconclusive. No tenderness to percussion or palpation could be discerned. Radiographically, osseous healing of the periapical lesion was evident as

well as root maturation ^[2,6,8,9]. The appearance of the mandibular left second premolar showed no obvious change in shade or colour (Figure 9).

Figure 6: Radiographic image taken at the six-month follow-up appointment. Resolution of the periapical radiolucency and some closure of the apex are evident.

Figure 7: Radiographic image taken at the 18-month follow-up appointment. Continued root maturation and resolution of the periapical radiolucency is evident.

Figure 8: Periapical film taken at the 18-month follow-up appointment.

Figure 9: Clinical photograph of teeth in the posterior segment of the left mandible taken at the 18-month follow-up appointment. When compared to pre operative stage there is no obvious change in shade or colour.

DISCUSSION

In 1961, Nygaard Ostby initially investigated the possibilities of regenerative endodontic therapy in necrotic teeth, but achieved very limited results. Histological study revealed that the formation of a functional pulp-dentine complex was

not consistently stimulated^[14]. Ongoing and prospective investigations in regenerative endodontics mostly revolve around the use of tissue engineering principles. These include techniques such as root canal revascularization, postnatal stem cell therapy, pulp implantation, scaffold implantation, injectable scaffold delivery, three-dimensional cell printing, and gene delivery^[15,16,17]. The clinician faces the task of identifying the potential of these novel therapies and integrating them into routine practice, where appropriate.

The present work, together with previous studies, provides evidence that regenerative endodontics is a feasible therapeutic alternative that has been characterized as a 'paradigm shift'. This approach enables ongoing root formation and the restoration of life and well-being in previously necrotic young teeth. Hargreaves et al. provide a comprehensive overview of several recurring elements that have been consistently observed and deemed significant in these investigations^[18]. First and foremost, the existence of a broad, unobstructed apex is highly probable as a necessary condition for the formation of tissue. Furthermore, due to the patients' youthful age, there is a likelihood of a significant capacity for stem cell regeneration. Furthermore, it is important to exercise caution in order to avoid damaging the walls of the canal. Sodium hypochlorite has been demonstrated to be a highly effective solution for irrigation purposes^[19]. Furthermore, it is advised against using calcium hydroxide as an intra-canal medicament. There is a concern that calcium hydroxide may have cytotoxic effects on viable pulp cells, particularly stem and progenitor cells located in the apical papilla, which are considered essential for further root maturation^[20]. Within the context of a study involving the application of calcium hydroxide, it was observed that the thickening of the dental wall exclusively took place at the apical region, namely up to the level where the medicament was administered. Furthermore, the use of a tri-antibiotic paste comprising ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and minocycline proves to be efficacious in eradicating bacteria from the contaminated root canal system. Ultimately, the formation of a blood clot can serve as a structural framework for tissue regeneration. Although not mentioned by Hargreaves et al., another recurring finding in these publications is the utilization of MTA to achieve a sufficient coronal seal, due to its well-established biological conductive characteristics.

Although these case reports have been categorized as either pulpal revascularization or regenerative endodontics with ongoing root growth and closure at the apex, the specific type of regenerated tissue remains uncertain. Several writers have proposed the presence of viable pulpal tissue in necrotic teeth that triggers the healing process. The value is 4.24. Undoubtedly, the ability of pulpal tissue to survive in teeth that are necrotic and/or pulpless has been widely recognized for a considerable period of time. Recent research on canine dentition has revealed that tissue ingrowth is more commonly derived from the periodontal ligament, which is composed of cementum, bone, and dentine-like substance, rather than from pulp tissue. According to these scientists, there is an estimated probability of around 30% for pulp tissue to re-enter the pulp space. The research conducted by this group has revealed that the canal dentinal walls in dogs were thickened due to the deposition of a tissue similar to cementum, which they referred to as 'intra-canal cementum'^[21].

Although there are limitations in our understanding, these case reports provide proof of the effectiveness of regenerative endodontic operations. However, the existing literature only consists of low levels of evidence, such as case series and case reports. Only a limited number of published publications have discussed the outcomes of the

regenerative technique, both in terms of success and failure. Jung et al. investigated the results of nine teeth, five of which had remaining living tissue. The therapy involved rinsing with sodium hypochlorite and applying tri-antibiotic paste as a medication. However, no irritation was induced to cause bleeding in the periapical tissues.⁵ In the four remaining teeth, where no living tissue could be observed, the procedure followed was identical, except that a blood clot was induced. All nine teeth showed no symptoms, and any apical periodontitis and draining sinuses that were present were resolved throughout a follow-up period of 1 to 5 years. Nevertheless, in a tooth lacking any remaining viable pulp, there was no apparent constriction of the root canal area, even though the apical periodontitis had resolved. Ding et al. analyzed 12 teeth that underwent regenerative endodontics, which involved rinsing with a solution containing 5.25% sodium hypochlorite and treating with a paste containing three antibiotics. The number is 8. Six patients withdrew from the research due to pain or inability to cause bleeding following canal disinfection. These patients underwent an apexification operation using the MTA barrier approach. Additionally, three patients did not show up for their scheduled follow-up sessions. The three surviving patients demonstrated full root growth, and their teeth showed responsiveness to pulp sensibility testing. Cheuh et al. employed 2.5% sodium hypochlorite to irrigate four teeth, while utilizing calcium hydroxide to cover a generated blood clot, without the usage of tri-antibiotic paste. Seven Although all four teeth showed continued root development and closure at the apex, the scientists observed that this only happened below the calcium hydroxide. Consequently, they concluded that the use of calcium hydroxide should be avoided as it may destroy potential progenitor cells ^[22]. Shah et al. conducted regenerative endodontics using an alternative approach. Fourteen teeth underwent irrigation with a solution containing 2.5% sodium hypochlorite and 3% hydrogen peroxide. Instead of using tri-antibiotic paste, formocresol was utilized as an inter-appointment medicament. During a follow-up period ranging from 0.5 to 3.5 years, the radiographic resolution of teeth was deemed to be satisfactory or outstanding in 93% (13 out of 14) of cases. Thickening of the dentinal walls was seen in 57% (8/14) of instances, whereas increased root length was noted in 71% (10/14) of cases. Randomized clinical trials and additional studies are clearly necessary to assess clinical outcomes and provide a standardized methodology. The American Association of Endodontists has initiated a database to allow physicians to provide information about their regenerative endodontic cases, assess various methods, and establish criteria for achieving the best results.

Curiously, the mentioned case reports do not commonly mention the use of ultrasonic irrigation, despite the fact that it has been proven to improve the cleaning and disinfection of the canal through the use of ultrasonic agitation of the irrigant. During the second treatment session, ultrasonication was employed due to the patient's discomfort, which could be attributed to the absence of mechanical preparation of the canal as specified in the protocol. To prevent harm to the canal walls, it is crucial to employ ultrasonics with little endosonic filing. Ding et al. documented two instances in which patients felt pain after the application of antibiotic paste, leading to the discontinuation of the regenerative endodontic operation in favor of conventional apexification methods. The number 8. The report did not include the use of endosonic irrigation, however, the authors proposed that this technique should be advised in upcoming clinical trials. This report indicates that the recommendation is valid, as the therapy effectively involved the use of ultrasonic activation of the irrigant.

This case presents a regenerative endodontic technique that achieved success by using a modified version of the tri-antibiotic paste established by Hoshino and colleagues¹⁶. In this case, amoxicillin was employed instead of minocycline. In this instance, there was no discernible alteration in color, which is commonly linked to minocycline. Nevertheless, the administration of amoxicillin is contraindicated in patients with a documented hypersensitivity to penicillin. Reynolds et al.⁹ used a different method to address discoloration. They started by applying 35% phosphoric acid (Ultra-Etch, Ultradent, South Jordan, UT, USA) to the dentinal tubules of the crown. Then, they sealed the tubules with SingleBond (3M, Minneapolis, MN, USA) and flowable composite (PermaFlo DC, Ultradent, South Jordan, UT, USA) before applying the tri-antibiotic paste. The authors also suggested using a 20G needle to backfill the tri-antibiotic paste in order to minimize the chances of placing it too high and causing potential discoloration. Synopsis

CONCLUSION

Dentists must acknowledge the significant potential of regenerative endodontics in treating necrotic, immature teeth. The initial approach should consist of irrigating with sodium hypochlorite only. Calcium hydroxide and other intra-canal medicaments should not be used since they hinder the formation of roots. This research utilizes a modified version of the tri-antibiotic paste, which is generally suggested for regenerative operations. The modification aims to prevent the discoloration of the crown that is typically associated with existing protocols. Regenerative endodontics, coupled with ongoing root growth, can potentially decrease the likelihood of fracture and premature tooth loss commonly associated with conventional 'apexification' techniques, which result in a thin and weak root structure.

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